

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT ISSUES IN SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article examines the role and importance of marketing strategies in the process of developing a supply chain in small businesses. The role of marketing activities in improving the efficiency of the supply chain, meeting customer needs, and ensuring competitiveness is analyzed. It also highlights the development opportunities of small businesses through market analysis, effective communication with customers, and the use of innovative marketing methods.

Keywords: small business, supply chain, marketing strategies, market analysis, customer needs.

Introduction. In today's globalized world, the importance of supply chain management for small businesses cannot be understated. A supply chain represents the network of all individuals, organizations, resources, and activities involved in creating and selling a product. For a small business, effective supply chain management means ensuring goods and services are delivered to the customer promptly, efficiently, and cost-effectively.

However, small businesses face unique challenges in managing their supply chains. These can range from resource constraints and logistical issues to technology implementation hurdles and fluctuations in demand and supply. Additionally, a lack of strategic planning and insufficient supplier relationship management can compound these issues, creating potential bottlenecks and inefficiencies.

Therefore, small businesses must prioritize effective strategies to overcome supply chain issues to maintain competitiveness. Such systems may include improving supplier relationships, implementing innovative supply chain technologies, using smart purchasing decisions, and optimizing inventory management. By investing time and resources in managing their supply chains effectively, small businesses can gain a competitive edge, reduce costs, and ultimately drive growth and profitability.

Literature review. Many foreign and domestic scholars are engaged in theoretical and practical research on the development of small business activities, supply chain management, and the revision of methodological aspects of supply chain management. We also conducted theoretical and empirical research during our research.

Dora Swami Naidu Raghavarapu, in his scientific works, put forward methodological foundations and models of marketing approaches to the management of supply processes and the development of supply chains. Fierce competition in today's global markets, the introduction of products with a short life cycle, and increasing customer expectations are forcing businesses to invest in and pay attention to their supply chains. This, along with ongoing advances in communication and transportation technologies (for example, mobile communications, the Internet, and delivery), has led to the continuous evolution of the supply chain and methods for its effective management [2].

D.Yu.Voronova also works on supply chain management systems, conducting research on the evolution of the supply chain system, approaches to supply chain management in Europe and Asia, and supply chain integration [3].

Another economist, T.T.Khashman, conducts research on supply chain management in logistics and lists the stages of supply chain management, including planning, sourcing, production, delivery, and returns. However, the

scientist does not take into account aspects of warehousing, order processing, and end consumption.

Analysis and results. Supply Chain Management (SCM) plays a critical role in the growth and sustainability of small businesses. However, small businesses often face unique challenges in managing their supply chains effectively. Below is an exploration of the main issues they encounter and potential solutions:

1. Limited Resources

- **Problem:** Small businesses often lack the financial and human resources to invest in sophisticated SCM systems or hire specialized personnel.
- **Impact:** Inefficient supply chain processes, delays, and higher operational costs.
- **Solution:**
 - Utilize cloud-based SCM software, which is more affordable and scalable.
 - Focus on key areas of improvement instead of attempting to optimize the entire supply chain at once.

2. Supplier Dependence

- **Problem:** Small businesses typically rely on a limited number of suppliers, leading to high dependency and vulnerability.
- **Impact:** Supply disruptions or unfavorable pricing due to the lack of bargaining power.
- **Solution:**
 - Diversify the supplier base to reduce risks.
 - Build collaborative relationships with suppliers to negotiate better terms and ensure reliability.

3. Inventory Management Challenges

- **Problem:** Inaccurate inventory tracking or overstocking/understocking due to a lack of advanced inventory systems.

- **Impact:** Increased storage costs, wastage, or lost sales opportunities.

- **Solution:**

- Implement basic inventory management tools to track stock levels and optimize ordering processes.
- Use just-in-time (JIT) inventory methods to reduce excess stock.

4. Demand Forecasting Issues

- **Problem:** Difficulty in predicting market demand due to a lack of data or expertise.

- **Impact:** Mismatch between supply and demand, leading to lost sales or excess inventory.

- **Solution:**

- Leverage historical sales data and market trends for demand forecasting.
- Collaborate with suppliers and customers to gain insights into demand patterns.

5. Logistics and Distribution Constraints

- **Problem:** Small businesses often face higher transportation costs and limited access to efficient logistics networks.

- **Impact:** Delayed deliveries and increased costs.

- **Solution:**

- Partner with third-party logistics (3PL) providers to access professional services at a lower cost.
- Optimize delivery routes and schedules to save time and money.

6. Technological Limitations

- **Problem:** Lack of access to advanced supply chain technologies such as automation, AI, or blockchain.

- **Impact:** Reduced efficiency and inability to compete with larger competitors.

- **Solution:**

- Start with affordable and user-friendly technologies, such as inventory tracking apps or CRM systems.

- Apply for grants or loans specifically aimed at digital transformation.

7. Regulatory and Compliance Challenges

- **Problem:** Navigating complex trade regulations, tariffs, or environmental standards can be daunting for small businesses.

- **Impact:** Delays or penalties due to non-compliance.

- **Solution:**

- Stay updated on regulations affecting the supply chain through industry associations or consultants.

- Use compliance management tools to simplify adherence.

8. Sustainability Pressures

- **Problem:** Increasing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly practices from consumers and regulators.

- **Impact:** Higher costs and operational challenges in adopting sustainable practices.

- **Solution:**

- Focus on cost-effective sustainability measures, such as reducing packaging waste or sourcing from local suppliers.

- Highlight sustainability initiatives in marketing to attract eco-conscious customers.

9. Risk Management Deficiencies

- **Problem:** Small businesses often lack formal risk management strategies for handling supply chain disruptions.

- **Impact:** Vulnerability to unexpected events such as natural disasters or economic downturns.

- **Solution:**

- Develop contingency plans for critical supply chain components.

- Invest in insurance to mitigate the financial impact of disruptions.

10. Scaling Challenges

- **Problem:** Rapid growth can strain supply chain operations that are not designed to handle increased demand.
- **Impact:** Service delays, quality issues, and customer dissatisfaction.
- **Solution:**
 - Gradually scale supply chain operations alongside business growth.
 - Seek mentorship or partnerships to handle growing pains.

Conclusion. Supply chain management is both a challenge and an opportunity for small business development. Addressing these issues through technology adoption, supplier diversification, and process optimization can significantly enhance efficiency and competitiveness. Small businesses should focus on building flexible and resilient supply chains to adapt to market changes and support long-term growth.

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